

UTILISING TRANSFORMER MODELS FOR CONTROLLABLE SCIENTIFIC ABSTRACTIVE SUMMARIZATION

S. Weidinger, S. Frank¹, ISDS, Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
A. Wagner, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland
C. Gütl, ISDS, Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
¹also at CERN, Geneva, Switzerland

Abstract

With the rapid pace of new publications, researchers face significant challenges in finding and extracting relevant information. However, the summarization of scientific texts remains challenging due to the complexity of domain-specific knowledge and length of the text, as well as the need for traceability of information back to the source. In this paper, we utilize SLED, an efficient long-document transformer approach, with the aim of facilitating more efficient information retrieval. SLED has demonstrated promising results according to the short document SCROLLS benchmark, as well as exceeding both extractive and abstractive baselines, offering a trade-off between performance and computational costs. Integration of semantic search methods can effectively identify original sentences, further enhancing the reliability and trustability of a system.

INTRODUCTION

Scientific research is essential for people who want to stay informed about scientific developments, but exploring and evaluating the wide selection of articles requires considerable time and effort. With the rapid pace of new publications, researchers face significant challenges in finding and extracting relevant information. Even considering filtering functions such as sorting by age or citations, traditional keyword-based search engines require users to explore countless results. Considering this, automatic summarization seems like a natural approach to tackle this challenge.

Automatic summarization aims to condense essential information from one or more documents into a concise and coherent summary. Although automatic summarization methods have received significant attention in the context of general text summarization, scientific articles present additional challenges that need to be considered. Document length, domain specificity, presence of complex or technical terminology, interconnected concepts, and often consistent structure present different challenges and opportunities and require additional consideration [1]. The need for attribution of information to its source further complicates the issue, as this traceability is essential for research. Aside from this, the rapid increase in computational costs of training or fine-tuning transformer-based language models makes considering economic solutions essential.

Research in long-text summarization is complicated by the shortage of datasets. Although some options exist, the focus on scientific articles, in particular, and the requirement of full-text data limit the selection. With this in mind,

we created two datasets for controllable scientific abstractive summarization and used them to train and test a new summarization model built on computer-science-centered articles. Our approach seeks to enhance the accessibility and usability of scientific literature, facilitating faster and more efficient information retrieval for researchers, scholars, and practitioners in various scientific disciplines.

In this paper, we present these datasets and explain the considerations that were made for their creation. Furthermore, we propose a method for low-resource, traceable scientific summarization along with experimental results showing its effectiveness and utility. We also discuss the implications of the findings and outline future research directions.

RELATED WORK

Although not as prevalent as general automatic summarization, long document summarization and the summarization of scientific articles have seen an increase in active research in recent years. In this section, we give an overview of the existing literature that covers one or both of the specific research fields.

Even outside of summarizing scientific search results, specifically, the summarization of long texts comes with challenges. Early approaches of automatic summarization methods usually focus on news articles that are significantly shorter than most scientific articles. Most commonly used models have a maximum token length of 1024. However, scientific articles have been found to have an average token length of around 10.7k [7]. This means that many of these methods are unusable for the summarization of full-text scientific articles due to the difference in length. This has created the task of the more specific *Long Document Summarization*, which typically requires more effort as knowledge requirements increase.

Previously studied methods for long-document summarization have used a variety of approaches to extract essential information while retaining coherence and key insights. LexRank, which was one of the first methods to find widespread use, calculated sentence similarity using graph-based methods to select the most important sentences [4]. More recently, advances in machine learning have enabled the development of transformer-based summarization models such as BERT [5], BART [6], and LongT5 [7]. All of these have had a significant impact on the field and gave rise to a plethora of fine-tuned models of their own. Although these methods have shown promising results in summarizing general and shorter text documents, such as news articles,

handling long documents remains a challenge due to the low token limit of most models and the rapid increase in computing costs.

Several studies have specifically addressed the task of summarizing scientific articles [9–12]. Even with the advances brought by transformer-based language models, the summarization of scientific text remains challenging due to the complexity of terminology, domain-specific knowledge, and the general length of the text, as well as the need for traceability for information. Specialized approaches are necessary. For example, Beltagy et al. (2019) introduced SciBERT, a pre-trained language model fine-tuned on scientific text, which demonstrated improved performance in various scientific NLP tasks, including summarization [8]. FacetSum, which was first presented in 2021 by Meng et al., placed a special focus on faceted summarization of scientific documents and was a fine-tuned version of BART, showed the best results for input consisting of introduction and conclusion, with full text input reaching lower scores [13]. In their recent work, Creo et al. evaluated the impact of prompting techniques on scientific summarization results and found that the use of decoder prompting led to improved performance, particularly for smaller summarization models [14].

However, even with these advances, handling long documents, capturing nuanced scientific concepts, enabling traceability of information, and creating coherent and informative summaries remain a challenge. Moreover, additional evaluation metrics and benchmarks are needed to assess the quality and effectiveness of scientific article summarization systems, as well as metrics to evaluate the factuality and allow traceability of information to provide the reliability of the summary that is essential for scientific contexts.

DEVELOPMENT

During the research stage, the focus was on using performant language models and explainable results. For this, it was necessary to look at the problem from two angles. For one thing, it was necessary to select a dataset according to a set of requirements. For another, a model or method had to be selected to be used for further processing/fine-tuning. In both cases, we made several considerations, which will be elaborated in the following.

Dataset Creation

After evaluating the existing datasets, it was found that they did not meet the requirements set in the context of this research. Either they do not meet the criteria of long-document collections, lack quality and diversity in their target summaries, or are sourced from a non-technical domain. Due to this, it was decided to create specialized datasets that included not only abstracts and/or conclusions, but the entire article text, as well as a focus on articles from the field of computer science.

Of the journals using *OpenReview*, a selection was made considering the focus on computer science domains, with four being determined for each dataset. The selected journals

are listed in Table 1, in part due to their higher number of past conferences, which implied more papers.

Although our new datasets *OpenReview Contribution* (1.7k) and *OpenReview Summary* (11k) are smaller than commonly used datasets such as ArXiv (215k) or PubMed (133k), they are comparable to more specialized datasets such as SciTLDR (3.2k) and FacetSum (5.8k) [13]. Uniquely, the OpenReview datasets provide multiple target summaries for each input document, not only for those contained in the test and validation splits such as SciTLDR. In particular, the dataset is divided into seven different summary lengths (described in Figure 2), facilitating length-controllable summary training. The data set was divided into training, validation, and testing sets using an 80-10-10 ratio. Furthermore, it should be noted that all summaries were crafted by academic experts, since access to the OpenReview website is restricted to academic members.

Model Selection

Although many approaches utilize very large language models, this usually comes with a high computing cost. In an effort to improve model accessibility, we placed emphasis on computing efficiency as well as what performance one can expect from these performant models when compared to the more common, larger models. In this study, we employ the efficient long-document transformer approach known as SLED [16]. SLED models utilize pre-trained, short-range encoder-decoder architectures, processing long-text input by dividing it into multiple overlapping chunks. Each chunk is encoded independently and then fused in the decoder phase (fusion-in-decoder). SLED has demonstrated promising results according to the long-document SCROLLS [18] benchmark, offering a trade-off between performance and computational cost. SLED using pre-trained BART models in the standard range as backbones compete with long-range transformers such as LongT5 [7] or UL2 [26], which have a larger parameter count. Moreover, the computational complexity is due to its fusion-in-decoder approach that is much smaller than that of standard transformer models with the same number of parameters, allowing higher input sizes with comparable computational costs. Additionally, it demonstrates better results than other efficient long-document transformers, such as LED [17], which are based on sparse attention.

The extractive summary is generated using a semantic search approach. This involves comparing the sentences from the abstractive summary with those of the original document. Initially, keywords are extracted from the abstractive summary using KeyBERT [23], leveraging SciDeBERTa [24] for nuanced scientific word contextualization. Candidate sentences that contain these keywords are then identified. Then, sentence embeddings are generated with SentBERT [25]. Finally, sentences are compared using cosine similarity and the most similar sentences are selected for inclusion in the extractive summary. This approach is called Sim. Search throughout this work and is depicted in Figure 1 in the post-processing step.

OpenReview Contribution	OpenReview Summary
	Neural Information Processing Systems
Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence	International Conference on Learning Representations
Automated Machine Learning	Medical Imaging with Deep Learning
Transactions on Machine Learning Research	Conference on Robot Learning

Table 1: Journals that were selected for inclusion in each dataset

STUDY

Based on the limitations determined during the review of related work, the focus was placed on efficient long-document summarization of scientific research articles that emphasized the traceability of summary sentences back to their source. The following research questions were defined:

- How do traditional small LLMs and efficient long-document models compare to elaborate models such as GPT?
- How can the traceability of information be emphasized for automatically created summaries?

Experimental Setup

Long-document summarization requires specialized language models, both because not all methods are able to cope with long-range dependencies and also because transformer-based models become infeasible due to resource limitations quickly. With this in mind, specific considerations had to be taken when the process was divided into components, as shown in Figure 1.

First, training the model required a specialized dataset that was created from scientific articles obtained from OpenReview¹. The text was extracted from the PDFs using the GROBID-based Python library *SciPDF parser*².

To test the SLED model and the semantic similarity search approach, namely Sim. Search, several abstractive and extractive standard methods are selected. The BART model, with an input size of around 1,000 tokens, serves as an abstractive and the standard extractive method. TextRank is used as an extractive baseline. The simple heuristic of using the abstracts of the articles provides an additional comparison measure. For text quality analysis, the methods are further compared with a large state-of-the-art GPT (*gpt-3.5-turbo-16k*³) model, capable of processing 16,000 tokens. In contrast, with the hardware setup in this work, the SLED model can handle up to 12,000 tokens. For evaluation, the GPT model was prompted to generate similar summaries in style and length using the provided API⁴ by OpenAI.

A central question in this study revolves around the comparison of text quality of smaller and more advanced large language models. The relatively small BART-base model has around 139 million parameters. Additionally, BART-base

Figure 1: System architecture. From “Analyzing Long-Document Transformer Models For Scientific Abstractive Summarization” by S. Weidinger, 2024, *Master’s Thesis*, p. 59

serves as the foundational model for SLED. Consequently, SLED encompasses the same number of parameters. In contrast, an initial version of the work by Singh et al. suggests that GPT-3.5-turbo has an impressive parameter count of approximately 20 billion [22].

To measure the performance of the methods, two metrics are applied: ROUGE [19] and BERTScore [20]. ROUGE is a set of lexical-based metrics that evaluate the overlap of n-grams, including ROUGE-1 and ROUGE-2, and the longest common subsequence (ROUGE-L). BERTScore calculates the similarity between reference and candidate summaries, using the BERT model *microsoft/deberta-large-mnli*⁵ for contextualization, as it shows high human correlation according to the Github repository⁶.

¹ <https://openreview.net/>

² https://github.com/titipata/scipdf_parser/tree/master

³ <https://platform.openai.com/docs/models/gpt-3-5>

⁴ <https://openai.com/blog/openai-api>

⁵ <https://huggingface.co/microsoft/deberta-large-mnli>

⁶ https://github.com/Tiiiger/bert_score

To evaluate the quality of text, we employ UniEval [21], a multidimensional deep learning-based evaluator. UniEval measures four key dimensions: coherence, factual consistency, fluency, and relevance. These dimensions collectively contribute to an overall quality score derived from their average values.

Findings and Discussion

Evaluation of the efficient transformer model SLED was carried out using ROUGE and BERTScore metrics on the OpenReview Contribution test set, comparing it to both extractive and abstractive baselines. Throughout the experiments, expert-crafted summaries served as the benchmark. The evaluation results, shown in Table 2, demonstrate the superior performance of SLED over all baselines in both metrics, particularly surpassing extractive methods by a significant margin. BART achieved results comparable to those of SLED on the ROUGE metric. However, when considering the similarity-based BERTScore metric, SLED exhibited a more substantial lead over BART, implying that SLED generates summaries that closely resemble human-crafted benchmark summaries and is better at copying their style and wording. Furthermore, the similarity search approach Sim. Search showed strong performance, outperforming TextRank and the heuristic method, although it fell short compared to SLED and BART. The results indicate that the similarity search approach effectively extracts meaningful information from the input text, generating good extractive summaries.

In particular, the abstracts of the articles proved to be a more suitable summary source compared to the outputs generated by TextRank, which received the lowest scores among all the evaluated methods. Thus, relying on the abstracts is generally more reliable than using TextRank summaries. Furthermore, the experiments confirmed that length-controllable summarization approaches improve the outcomes, yielding more valuable summaries. When using a length token as guide signal, significant improvements were observed in both ROUGE and BERTScore metrics.

Additionally, a detailed analysis was conducted to assess the performance of each method in various summary lengths. As shown in Figure 2, the SLED model consistently outperforms other methods regardless of the summary length, with the heuristic method yielding comparable results, particularly in very long summaries. Consequently, for scientific articles, automatic summarization techniques prove more advantageous for shorter recaps, given that the abstracts of articles are typically lengthy and already encompass essential information. Additionally, it should be noted that the similarity search approach demonstrates effectiveness for shorter summaries, although its relevance diminishes with longer recaps. Nevertheless, Sim. Search consistently produces results that are either better or comparable to those of the heuristic method and abstractive models, proving that semantic search is an effective approach to finding sentence origins.

For evaluation purposes of summary text quality, a subset of the OpenReview Contribution test set was selected that consists of 91 randomly chosen summaries along with their corresponding articles. These summaries are classified under the label "long" containing between 90 and 125 words each. The evaluation assesses the quality of these summary texts in terms of coherence, factual consistency, fluency, and relevance. The summaries composed by experts serve as a benchmark. The results are shown in Table 3. Although the abstracts of the articles are of superior quality on average, they often lack fluency and relevance. Notably, among automatic summarization methods, GPT followed by SLED demonstrate the most impressive results, particularly excelling in fluency and relevance. Both GPT and SLED consistently produce more pertinent summaries with high-quality sentences. From Table 3, it is evident that the summary texts generated by the extractive methods exhibit deficiencies in coherence and relevance. However, the similarity search method shows higher factual consistency compared to SLED and BART. This suggests that simply extracting phrases from input texts can enhance the system's factuality and increase trustworthiness. Furthermore, it should be noted that language models with fewer parameters can rival larger, more complex models such as GPT in terms of text quality. As illustrated in Table 3, SLED scores only 3.36 points less in the overall score, demonstrating comparable performance despite its smaller size. Surprisingly, the standard range model BART demonstrates nearly identical overall performance compared to the long-document model SLED. However, a deeper investigation revealed that BART tended to hallucinate in around ten percent of the summaries by creating human-like comments, primarily to fulfill the length requirement. These comments and annotations were incorporated by experts in some samples to provide additional information to the authors of the articles and were learned during the training by the models. On the contrary, SLED generated hallucinatory annotations in only about one percent of cases. Therefore, SLED, in contrast to BART, included more relevant content of the input and consequently produced more informative summaries overall. As a result, long-document models are needed to capture the essential information, often incorporated in the results and conclusion, hence, in the end of the articles.

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study found that large language models (LLMs) with relative low parameter count and computational costs can produce competitive results when compared to large sophisticated models such as GPT. In particular, the efficient long-document transformer SLED, employing the fusion-in-decoder technique, exhibited impressive performance that exceeded both extractive and abstractive baselines. SLED showcases its proficiency in capturing long-distance relationships and generating highly relevant summaries, outperforming standard range models such as BART. Furthermore, the integration of semantic search methods can effectively

Method	Input source	Length signal	ROUGE1	ROUGE2	ROUGELsum	BERTScore
heuristic	paper abstr.	no	32.73	9.39	20.23	0.220
TextRank	full paper	no	29.09	6.21	19.26	0.114
TextRank	full paper	yes	30.95	6.52	20.41	0.128
Sim. Search	summ.+paper	yes	35.77	9.60	23.44	0.229
BART _{base}	1K tokens	yes	36.81	10.45	33.06	0.276
SLED _{base}	12K tokens	no	32.68	9.90	29.40	0.268
SLED _{base}	12K tokens	yes	36.95	10.81	33.12	0.282

Table 2: Performance evaluation was conducted on the OpenReview Contribution test set. SLED surpasses both extractive baselines and BART in terms of ROUGE and BERTScore metrics, underscoring SLED’s ability to effectively capture long-term dependencies. The similarity search approach Sim. Search shows strong performance, outperforming both TextRank and heuristic methods. The inclusion of a length signal significantly improved overall performance.

Figure 2: Performance comparison across summary lengths, conducted using the OpenReview Contribution dataset. The dataset was automatically divided into seven bins, with slight adjustments for better label balance. The lengths were classified according to bin sizes as follows: "brief" - [0, 40), "very short" - [40, 55), "short" - [55, 70), "middle" - [70, 90), "long" - [90, 125), "very long" - [125, 200), and "extra long" - [200, ∞). SLED consistently outperformed other methods on average, regardless of summary size.

Method	Type	#Params	Coherence	Consistency	Fluency	Relevance	Average
paper abstr.	extr.	-	94.19	94.35	88.80	85.42	90.69
TextRank		-	40.36	68.28	76.71	35.82	55.29
Sim. Search		-	61.55	82.91	87.55	55.21	71.80
GPT _{zero-shot}	abstr.	~20B	<u>92.37</u>	<u>84.47</u>	91.63	91.52	<u>90.00</u>
BART _{base}		139M	90.22	82.84	86.11	86.81	86.49
SLED _{base}		139M	89.08	80.99	<u>88.93</u>	<u>87.54</u>	<u>86.64</u>

Table 3: Text quality was compared based on the dimensions coherence, consistency, fluency and relevance. Summaries composed of experts serve as a benchmark. While the abstracts of the articles generally exhibited superior quality, they were often deficient in fluency and relevance. In particular, among automatic summarization methods, GPT followed by SLED showed the most impressive results, demonstrating strong performance, particularly in fluency and relevance.

identify original sentences, thereby enhancing the reliability and trustability of the system.

However, the fusion-in-decoder approach is constrained by its contextual window, which may cause it to fail to establish accurate long-distance connections. Future research should be done to evaluate models that incorporate alternative efficient methods for long-document processing. Additionally, the method of searching for similar sentences

based solely on entire sentences in the input text fails to capture sentence fusion and shortening, noticeably limiting performance. Moreover, traceability could help to improve the factual consistency in abstractive summaries by incorporating facts from the original sentences. Addressing these points could further improve the overall performance of the system.

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